

DETERMINANTS OF HOLDING PERIOD BEHAVIOR WITH MODERATING YIELD TO MATURITY IN OPEN MANUFACTURING COMPANIES INDONESIA AND MALAYSIA

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the effect of Bid Ask Spread, Market value, and Variance Return, Dividend payout ratio on Holding Period with Yield to Maturity as a moderating variable. The type of data used is secondary data in the form of financial statements of companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange and the Malaysia Stock Exchange. The independent variables of this study are the Bid Ask Spread, Market Value, Variance Return, and Dividend Payout Ratio. The dependent variable of firm value is measured by the Holding Period. While partially Bid Ask Spread, Variance Return and Dividend Payout Ratio have a positive and significant effect on the Holding Period. Market Value has a positive but not significant effect on the Holding Period.

Keywords: Bid Ask Spread, Market Value, Variance Return, Dividend Payout Ratio, Yield to Maturity, Holding Period, Indonesia Stock Exchange, Malaysia Stock Exchange

INTRODUCTION

In this era of globalization, all sectors experience changes and developments, one of the most significant sectors of development has occurred in the manufacturing industry, so that investors face various challenges. Investors who invest not only see their investment, the rate of return or the risk obtained, psychological factors also determine the investment. Therefore, investment analysis that uses the psychology of financial science is known as behavioral or behavioural.

With the development of investment, financial behavior plays a very important role in making investment decisions. Behavioral finance aims to understand people's behavior in making investment decisions. Behavioral finance is a relatively new field of science that aims to combine theories from cognitive behavioral psychology with economics and conventional finance to explain how people make irrational financial decisions. An investor who invests in shares will receive a profit, namely a capital gain and this is indicated by the decision of investors who tend to have a longer tenure of shares. On the other hand, if investors believe that the stock's performance is not good, then investors should sell their shares faster, namely by holding shares for a short time.

The criteria that are owned by companies listed in Indonesia are the highest average capitalization, based on the average daily transaction value in the market of companies listed in the stock index that have a leverage ratio disposition that tends to be more and more

desirable because it tends to be relative to other companies listed on the stock index. Better development of the capital market plays an important role in increasing economic growth because capital has 2 functions, namely the function and the financial function. Meanwhile, in carrying out its financial function, the capital market provides the necessary funds to parties who need funds, and those who have the advantage of providing funds without having to be directly in the real assets needed for investment. In the implementation process,

A continuous auction system or what is commonly referred to as a continuous auction system is that the transaction price of a particular security is determined by the supply and demand of investors. In the mechanism of this trading system, it is called the bid price, which is the high price that the buyer is asked to buy and the price which the lowest price is offered by the seller to sell. The amount of the difference between the bid price and the ask price, hereinafter referred to as the bid-ask spread, is influenced by considerations related to investment decisions made by investors in achieving optimal returns or net returns and reducing the level of risk as low as possible. The difference between the selling price and the purchase price affects the level of stock liquidity.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Behavior Finance (Behaviour Finance)

Behavioural finance is a model that emphasizes the potential implications of psychological factors that influence investor behavior. Investors are assumed to be willing and able to receive and all information is available based on them. But in reality, investors often show things that are irrational, so this situation deviates from the assumption of rationality and tends to be biased. Behavioral finance studies how humans behave in financial decisions, in particular studying how psychology affects financial decisions, business, and investors.

Holding Period

If the share price is lower than its value then the shares must be purchased and temporarily held for the purpose of obtaining capital gains if the price later recovers. If the stock market price is its intrinsic value, then don't do it because the shares are balanced, so there is no profit from the stock sale and purchase transaction. If the market price of a stock is higher than its intrinsic value, the stock must be sold to avoid a loss. Before making this investment, investors must first obtain information about shares, such as the issuing company, published financial statements and other information that is considered to influence the decision to buy shares. This information is important to know whether the stock will provide optimal returns to investors.

Yield To Maturity

Bond yields are the rate of return we receive. Thus, the higher the return value, the higher the interest we get and vice versa. Meanwhile, yield to maturity is the yield that investors will get from bonds held by investors until maturity. Yield to maturity is the rate of return that investors will receive if they buy bonds at the market price and hold the bonds until maturity. The structure of interest rate risk is generally the yield spread, which is defined as the

relationship between bond yields and certain characteristics of the bond, such as quality, maturity, coupon and ease with which the bond can be traded.

Bid Ask Spread

The bid price is the highest price per dialer while the ask price is the lowest price. The Bid Ask Spread is the difference between the bid price and the ask price. The market spread is the difference between the highest bid and the lowest ask occurring at a given time. The bid-ask spread reflects the costs of creating a market, including the cost of information asymmetry, the cost of inventory imbalances, the cost of processing orders may be monopoly leases. Dealers are parties who in the implementation of buying and selling of equity securities hold a significant share of the capital market. Direct costs, direct costs, are commissions for brokers plus taxes. Bid Ask Spread, investors buy at the time of asking and selling at the time of offering. High prices affect the sale or purchase.

Market Value

Market value is the price of actions that occur in the stock market at a certain maturity of transaction activity in the market. This is in accordance with the theory of the efficient hypothesis, namely the investment theory which states that it is impossible to "beat the market" because stock efficiency causes stock prices to move on the existing action will always reflect all relevant information. By investing in the capital market, investors tend to choose shares of large business entities that have better stability in the parameters of the distribution of returns. The higher the market value of a stock, the more investors tend to hold it for longer.

Variance Return

Stock return variance is a parameter of stock price movement that reflects the company's risk. In theory, a high stock return spread will result in a longer stock holding period. This is in accordance with the statement that the higher a stock is, the faster the investor will release the stock, and conversely, the lower the risk of the stock held by the investor for a longer period of time. Risk is the difference between the rate of return and the actual rate of return. Return risk is the level of risk arising from an investment activity. To determine the level of risk faced by investors, the stock returns must first be calculated.

Dividend Payout Ratio

Dividends are part of the operating profit obtained and deposited by the company to its shareholders in return for their willingness to invest their assets in the company. The theory above strengthens the statement that the dividend payout ratio is the percentage of dividends paid by the company to shareholders.

METHOD APPROACH

The approach used in this research is quantitative. where the research data is in the form of numbers to be measured using statistics as a test calculation tool, relating to the problem under study to produce a conclusion. This research was conducted at the Indonesia Stock

Exchange and the Malaysia Stock Exchange through the internet with the sites www.idx.co.id and www.bursamalaysia.com.

Effect of Bid Ask Spread on Holding Period

The thing that investors have to pay attention to is to decide whether to buy or sell at a certain price to find out what the difference is between the buying price and the selling price. Stocks that have high spreads are more likely to be held by investors for a longer period of time. The high cost of information reflects a high level of information and is indicated by a greater stock dispersion.

Effect of Market Value on Holding Period

Companies with high market value are considered big companies and have a broader range of analysts so that they can produce financial reports and that will reduce the gap between investors' expectations and what is actually happening in the company. Companies that have a high market value have a large company size. On the other hand, companies with small market value have small company sizes. A high stock price sends a signal to investors that they are choosing to hold more of the stock they hold.

Effect of Variance Return on Holding Period

Basically, all investors who invest always expect high returns. However, in investing, the return is always associated with what will be borne by the investor. Do these investors like high risk for return or do they avoid risk to a certain degree. But in general, all investors refused. Calculating the return from variance is a way to determine the level of risk arising from an investment. According to Wisayang, theoretically, the development of a high stock spread will lead to the shortest holding period.

Effect of Dividend Payout Ratio on Holding Period

Dividend payout ratio is a factor that must be considered by investors as long as investors hold their shares. Providing adequate dividends may be one of the considerations for

investors when buying and holding their shares. With this condition, investors will hold longer ownership of the company's shares and will distribute dividends in one period.

Effect of Bid-ask Spread on Holding Period with Yield to Maturity as Moderating Variable

If investors perceive that investing in a company is low risk, such as investing in government bonds, then investors do not need a large return to offset their investment, but on the other hand, if investors see that in a company involves high risk, participants will demand higher rewards. high , adjusted for what they support, i.e. higher yield differences.

Effect of Market Value on Holding Period with Yield to Maturity as Moderating Variable

Changes in bond prices in the market are strongly influenced by changes in interest rates and perceptions of risk. Bond prices in the capital market can be higher or lower than their nominal value. Bonds can be traded at any time above or below their par value, depending on market conditions. The longer the time, the higher the interest rate to cover the additional risk due to the investment period itself.

Effect of Variance Return on Holding Period with Yield to Maturity as Moderating Variable

Bond ratings reflect the risk of nonpayment of interest or principal, hence bond prices in the opposite direction. It therefore determines that the longer the maturity date, the higher the yield-to-maturity risk in the bond because fluctuations in the yield-to-maturity are higher in the longer term. If inflation tends to increase, the number of bonds will be as fast as possible because if inflation increases, then at maturity it will also increase.

Effect of Dividend Payout Ratio on Holding Period with Interest Rate as Moderating Variable

Stock prices are very volatile in the face of various economies, both micro and macro. Changes in bond prices in the market due to interest rates and inflation. When the company is not making a profit, the shareholders do not receive the dividends while the interest and principal are payable regardless of the profit or loss of the business.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Multicollinearity Test Results

Variable	VIF
BASS	1.039566
MV	1.019933
VR	1.012295
DPR	1.048273

Source: E Views 12 Software Results

Table 1 shows that the results of the multicollinearity test, it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity between the independent variables. This is because the VIF value < 10.

Table 2. Autocorrelation Test Results with Durbin-Watson Test

Log Likelihood	-207.4692	Hannan-Quinn Criter.	2.040876
		Durbin-Watson Stat	1.999979

Source: E Views 12 Software Results

Table 2 shows that the result the value of the Durbin-Watson statistic is 1.999979. Note that because the value of the Durbin-Watson statistic lies between 1 and 3, i.e. $1 < 1.999979 < 3$, the non-autocorrelation assumption is met. In other words, there is no high autocorrelation symptom in the residuals.

Table 3. Moderation Test Results (Indonesia and Malaysia)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	1.823819	0.084264	21.64410	0.0000
BASS	0.039933	0.037861	1.054734	0.0001
MV	0.006994	0.008877	0.787941	0.4314
VR	0.316060	0.384093	0.822874	0.0321
DPR	0.094909	0.104794	0.905668	0.0000
YTM	-0.559923	0.349157	-1.603644	0.1099
M1	0.546820	0.200868	2.722292	0.0069
M2	-0.047161	0.043363	-1.087584	0.2777
M3	1.437964	1.169132	1.229942	0.2198
M4	-0.219492	0.314486	-0.697940	0.4858

Source: E Views 12 Software Results

Table 3 shows that Yield to maturity significantly moderates the effect of the bid ask spread on the holding period (Prob. $0.0069 < 0.05$). Yield to maturity does not significantly moderate the effect of market value on the holding period (Prob. $0.2777 > 0.05$). Yield to maturity does not significantly moderate the effect of variance return on holding period (Prob. $0.2198 > 0.05$). Yield to maturity does not significantly moderate the effect of dividend payout ratio on holding period (Prob. $0.4858 > 0.05$).

CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion of the research results that have been described in the previous section, it can be concluded that the bid-ask spread, market value, dividend yield simultaneously affect the holding period in Malaysian-Indonesian manufacturing companies. All independent variables, namely bid-ask spread, market, yield variance, dividend rate simultaneously have a significant effect on the holding period of manufacturing companies and Malaysia. The bid-ask spread is known to have a significant positive effect on the holding period of Malaysian manufacturers and companies. The market value is known to be positive and insignificant during the holding period of Indonesian and Malaysian manufacturing companies. The return variance is known to have a positive and significant effect on the holding time of Indonesian and Malaysian manufacturing companies.

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